

Self-esteem of Visually Disabled Adolescents in Manipur

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Abstract – Self-esteem is an organised collection of beliefs, feelings of one-self which makes the individual aware of continuing identity as a person, it is the central scheme in one's personality. It refers to an individual's sense of his or her value or worth or to extend to which a person's value, approves, appreciates, prizes or like himself or herself. Adolescence is the period during which a younger person develops sense of identity and feeling of self-worth and self-esteem. As adolescence being a stage of tremendous physical, cognitive and effective changes in identity and self-image, visually disabled adolescents faces difficulties on many of basic functioning. They can't satisfy of many of basic emotional and social needs thus become victims of low self-esteem. The disability condition affects one's self-esteem and negative self-evaluation. This paper examines the self-esteem of visually disabled adolescents and the impact of age, sex, academic achievement of the adolescents on self-esteem. Random sampling technique was used and 60 samples of age group 12-19 years were collected with the Sorensen "Self-esteem Test 2006" from the disabled institutions/centres situated in Imphal East and Imphal West Districts of Manipur, India. The data collected was analysed by using SPSS (version 25.0). Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, percentage as well as t'-test and correlation have been adopted to measure the results more efficiently and accurately and to test the hypotheses. Findings reported that lower self-esteem of the visually disabled adolescents. There

was impact of age, sex, and academic achievement of the adolescents on self-esteem level. Thus, the results could analyse about the impact factors on self-esteem of the visually disabled adolescents. The study suggested that special needs education system should be incorporated in the curriculum so as to enhance the self-esteem, live skills, co-curricular activities suitable for the disability environment. Moreover, the disabled institutions/centres must develop different mechanisms of creating a conducive environment specially designed for the disabled students. As a whole, the institutions should provide facilities to recognise and acceptance of the disabled adolescents in the society.

Keywords: Self-esteem, Visually Disabled, Adolescents, Personality and Manipur.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is one of the crucial periods one must achieve the attitude and beliefs needed for effective participation in a society. The way every individual passes through it with the help of people around him/her determines how better the person's youth and adult periods will look like. It is the unique period in life cycle that presents especially challenges and opportunities to the individuals.

World Health Organisation (WHO) defined adolescences as the period between the ages of 10-19 years and is a period of transition from childhood and adulthood. It is the period of rapid intellectual growth and characterized by an increase in

personal control, responsibilities, and independence. [1]

Adolescence is the period which a younger person develops sense of identity and feeling of self-worth and self-esteem. As the adolescence being a stage of tremendous physical, cognitive, and effective changes in identity and self-image, or visually disabled adolescents face difficulties in many of basic functioning's. They cannot satisfy many of basic emotional and social needs thus become victims of low self-esteem. The disability condition affects one's self-esteem and negative self-evaluation.

Visual impairment/vision impairment (visually disabled) is a medical definition measured on an individual's better eye visual acuity; in the absence of treatment such as correctable eyewear, assistive devices and medical treatment. Visual impairment causes the individual difficulties with normal daily tasks including reading and working. [2]

The American Academy of Ophthalmology defines visual impairment as the best-corrected visual acuity of less than 20/40 in the better eye. [3] And WHO defines it as a presenting acuity of less than 6/12 in the better eye. [4]

Self-esteem is the evaluation we make of ourself or the degree to which we perceived ourselves positively or negatively our overall attitudes in the direction of ourselves. Self-esteem is an organized collection of beliefs, feelings of one's self-esteem which makes the individual aware of continuing identity as a person. It is the central scheme in one's personality. Self-esteem reflects a person's overall subjective emotional evaluation of his/her own worth. It is the judgement of oneself as well as an attitude towards the self. Individuals with high self-esteem have a clean intellect of what their private qualities are they think well of themselves, have appropriate goals, use feedbacks mechanism to enhancing self (Wood, & Hem pet 2003. [5] The idea of self-starts growing from the period of infancy and keeps on growing till and through adolescence and maturity. Adolescence being critical period of development highlights a strong relationship

between self-esteem and feeling of disablement like vision impairment and which interactively produces significant effect on the personal and social adjustment of the Visually adolescents.

The social impact on physically challenged persons is one of the most important parts of actual problems and social support is one of the important focus points which makes them feel more effective and enhance them in all aspects of their adjustment in the society.

How effective the visually disabled adolescents feel is an important part of development and helps to cope with life's difficulties and positively motivates them for betterment of life around him. But their disability blocks them from performing their activities successfully in life. In such case of life's difficulty situation there needs to study the self-esteem level of such marginalised groups as it helps in one's life. High/positive self-esteem possessors have more personality development and can adjust life in any difficulty situations.

So, this leads the proposed research question for studying the self-esteem of visually disabled adolescents in Manipur and what needs to be adopted and state suitably for the development in living styles and in educational atmosphere in order to develop and increase the level of self-concept, self-reliance, self-esteem and self-sufficient in their life in spite of the physical disabilities.

1.1 Significance of the Study

According to APA having high self-esteem in one's life is the keyway to better mental health and well being. It also helps in coping life skills, can handle life's adversity, and can remove negative thoughts which can be turned into perspective way. [6] Self-esteem influences motivation as people with healthy, positive view of themselves understands their potential and may feel inspired to take on new challenges. Self-esteem helps in the motivation to develop oneself for betterment of adjusting around his surroundings. It influences behaviour, thinking and actions of individual in very aspects of human life. Self-esteem is a condition that promotes good

performances especially in stress situations. It enables one to remove the inferiority complex to draw upon one's unique strength and confidence to cope with life's difficulties and work for betterment for himself and of those around him.

Self-esteem builds oneself to think optimistic attitudes makes person self-motivated, increase risk taking ability and improves performances in life. Being even in disability condition the visually disabled adolescents need to enhance self-esteem in higher condition, encouragement from parents, teachers, friends and caretakers removing inferiority complexes in and around his surroundings from them. Different requirements, plans need to be enforced or supported to cope up their life conditions and situations at least to remove the inequalities from the normal peer groups in the society.

1.2 Objectives

The study aims:

- To find out self-esteem level of the visually disabled adolescents.
- To find out the self-esteem among the boys and girls adolescents.
- To find out the self-esteem among younger and older groups of the adolescents.
- To study the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement of the adolescents.

1.3 Hypotheses

The present study seeks to verify the following hypotheses:

- H₁: There exists low self-esteem of visually disabled adolescents.
- H₂: There is difference on self-esteem among the sex of the adolescents.
- H₃: There is difference on self-esteem among boys and girls.
- H₄: There is relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement of the adolescents.

1.4 Methodology

Research method: To achieve the above cited objectives of the study, descriptive survey method in explorative nature was used.

Population: The population of the study has covered all visually disabled adolescents who got registered in special schools of disabled in Imphal East and Imphal West Districts of Manipur in both Government and Non-Government centres.

Sample: The sample size of the present study was limited to 60 visually disabled adolescents each of 30 boys and 30 girls from the age group of 12-19 years which were drawn from The Govt. Ideal Blind School, Takyelpat, Imphal West District, Manipur, and Spastic Society of Manipur, Tapokpi Bazar, Imphal East, Manipur. Random Sampling Technique was used for the data collection.

Tools: the tools used for the data collection were-

1. Sorensen Self-esteem Test constructed by Sorensen in 2006.
2. Basic Data Sheets explaining the Age, Sex and Academic Achievement of the adolescents was used for detailed information.

2. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The researcher classified, tabulated the data for presenting analysis systematically. The data was classified on the basis of age sex and academic achievers, among of the respondents. Mean, Standard Deviation, t'-test and correlations were used for the statistical inferences and descriptions.

Table – I: Statistical differential indicating Mean, Standard Deviation and percentage value of:

Self-esteem level of the Visually Disabled Adolescents

Self-esteem level	f'	%	M	SD
Mild low	11	18.3	11	7.8
Moderately low	25	41.7		
Severely low	24	40.0		
Total	60	100.0		

'f' = Frequency, % = Percentage, M = Mean

Interpretation:

From the above Table -1, it can be revealed that 41.7% of the visually disabled adolescents were in the moderately low self-esteem, while 18.3% were in the mild low self-esteem and 40% of them were in the severely low self-esteem level. Thus, it can be concluded that visually disabled adolescents had lower self-esteem. Therefore, hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Table - 2: Statistical differential indicating Mean, Standard Deviation, 't'-test and p-value of Self-esteem level and Sex of the adolescents

Sex	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value
Girls	30	18.80	8.10	0.70	0.48
Boys	30	17.43	6.98		

significant at 0.05 level of significance

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the mean value and the SD value of the girl adolescent are 18.80 and 8.10 and that of the boys 17.43 and 6.98 respectively. This shows that there is difference in self-esteem between boys and girl adolescents. The obtained 't' value is 0.70, which is significant at 0.05 level and p-value stands at 0.48. So, it can be concluded that there is difference on the self-esteem level among the sex of the adolescents. Hence hypothesis 2 is accepted that there is difference between boys and girl. Girls have better self-esteem than boys.

Table - 3: Statistical differential indicating Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' test value of-

Self-esteem Level of Visually Disabled Adolescents in relation to Age of the Adolescents

Sex	Age group	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value
Girls	12-15	15	22.60	7.71	2.875	0.008
	16-19	15	15.00	6.74		
Boys	12-15	15	15.00	8.13	2.008	0.054
	16-19	15	19.87	4.69		

significant at 0.05 level of significance

Interpretation:

The Table -3 depicts that the means of the self-esteem scores of the younger group adolescent girls is 22.60 and older group girls is 15 and their SDs is 7.71 and 6.74 respectively, 't'-value between the means is 2.875 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Moreover, the mean value of the younger group boys is 15 and older group boys is 19.89 and SDs value is 8.13 and 4.69 respectively and 't'-value between the means is 2.008 which is significant at 0.05 level. Thus, from the results it can be concluded that there is difference on the self-esteem level that older group adolescents both from boys and girls have better self-esteem level. Thus, hypothesis -3 is accepted.

Table - 4: Statistical differential indicating Mean, Standard Deviation and Co-efficient of Correlation value of -

Self-esteem and Academic Achievement among Visually Disabled Adolescents

Variables	No.	Mean	SD	Correlation
Self-Esteem	60	15	11.02	0.96
Academic Achievement	60	15	10.42	

significant at 0.05 level of significance

Interpretation:

The above table shows the mean value, the SD value and Correlation value of Self-esteem of Boys and Girls from among the locomotor disabled adolescents. The Correlation value is 0.96, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence the hypothesis 4 is accepted, that there would be positive relationship

between Self-esteem and Academic Achievement among the visually disabled adolescents.

3. MAJOR FINDINGS

1. Visually disabled adolescents have lower self-esteem.
2. There is significant difference between the sex of the adolescents and self-esteem of the adolescent that the girls have better self-esteem than the boys.
3. There is significant difference between the age of the adolescents and self-esteem of the adolescents that older group both from boys and girls have better self-esteem level than the younger ones.
4. There is correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. From the findings of the research, some conclusions appear tenable to the parents, administrators, educationalist and stake holders to promote achievements and making concerns for the disabled persons in the society. Parents should adopt good parenting styles to their children and need to encourage to systematically institutionalising their wards, for better adaptation in the society and to increase the self-esteem of their children.
2. Stakeholders, Govt. sectors also need to take up projects for the welfare and upliftment of status for such marginalised sections of people in their education sector as well as job seeking opportunities suitably with their condition and standard.

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://www.britania.com/science-Adolescence/Definition, characteristics & stages/britanica>.
- [2] "Vision impairment and blindness/examination - based studies/Information on data sources/vision and eye health surveillance system/vision health initiative [VHI] CDC" <†.www.cdc.gov2021-08-10 retrived 2022-03-03.
- [3] "Low vision, American Academy of Ophthalmology <†. www.aao.org.retrived 2022-03-03.
- [4] "Vision Impairment and Blindness" <†www.who.int.retrived 2022-03-03.
- [5] Wood, J.V. ..., and Hem pet, S.A. (2003). Savoring verses dampering self-esteem differences in regulating positive affect, Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 85, pp 556 -580.
- [6] <https://www.verywellmind.com>w..>].